

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University,
Czech Republic

Proposed Gene-Environment definitions

- **Genome:** the complete set of genes or genetic material of a biological entity
- **Genotype (G):** the genes or genetic material of a biological entity at a given timepoint
- **Genes:** a unit of heredity which is transferred from a parent to offspring
- **Heredity:** the passing on of traits/ characteristics genetically from one generation to another
- **Exposome:** the complete set of exposures of a biological entity
- **Exposotype (E):** the exposures of a biological entity at a given timepoint
- **Exposure:** a unit of contact between external factors and a biological entity
- **Non-genetic inheritance:** the passing of traits/ characteristics non-genetically from one generation to another
- **Phenome:** the complete set of traits/characteristics displayed by a biological entity
- **Phenotype (P):** the traits/characteristics displayed by a biological entity at a given timepoint

$$P_t = F(G_{<t}, E_{<t}, G_{<t} \times E_{<t})$$

The phenotype at time t is a functional combination (F) of genotype history, exposotype history, and their interaction over time.